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EXPANDING THE NATURE OF EDUCATION THROUGH SPECIALIZED CAPABILITY

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Abstract: Schools are unique and complicated establishments. They are complicated because madrasas are organizational structures with a number of interconnected and mutually determining dimensions. In contrast, madrasas are one-of-a-kind institutions because they possess certain characteristics that other organizations lack. This study centers around administrative abilities in working on the nature of schooling, with the focal point of exploration: How are the endeavors of the Madrasah Head to work on the nature of schooling through specialized abilities. Clear planning, as outlined in the vision, mission, and objectives, as well as the use of the appropriate strategy—empowering existing human resources, forming teams, minimizing problems, and continuous improvement through program evaluation—are key to improving education quality.

Keywords: quality education first; empowering; ability as a manager; technical know-how.

INTRODUCTION

When we talk about education, we have to talk about a lot of related things as well. The head of the madrasah is a leader who is directly involved in the teaching and learning process as an executor and who manages and supports the Madrasah staff with a full sense of responsibility. so that the madrasah's education program runs smoothly. Leadership management of the madrasah head is necessary for the smooth operation of madrasah management. Lead and leader are the two parts of the word "leadership" together. According to Alwi Hasan et al., leading is the act of guiding, knowing, or directing, heading, and walking in front of the person being led. The leader, on the other hand, is the individual who provides guidance, provides knowledge. The following is Hifza's definition of leadership: mentioning the skills of a leader that set them apart from other leaders. This is how the different types of leadership differ in their character, so there are differences between the types and styles of leadership. These differences are not just in the type of leadership they have, but also in the type of leadership they are (Hifza Juliana et al., 2020; Hutagaluh and others, 2020; Suhardi, Hifza, and others, 2020; Dewi and team, 2020; 2020, Hifza and Aslan; Hutagaluh and Aslan, 2019). Therefore, the term "leadership" refers to the manner in which a principal of a madrasah directs, guides, provides, or is aware of the activities that have been delegated to him in order to improve the madrasah's management (Bendapudi et al., 2006; Gearhart and other, 2012; Hogg and others, 2017).

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The head of the madrasah is the leader of an educational institution whose primary responsibility is to manage Madrasah management coordinates all staff and students in the madrasah; consequently, he must be able to direct and bring about a led institution that is superior and more advanced. The head of a madrasah or madrasah is the person in charge of an educational establishment. Their primary responsibilities include overseeing the teaching and learning process, managing students, coordinating all staff (teachers and employees), overseeing facilities and infrastructure, overseeing finances, collaborating with the community, and overseeing special services. The head of the madrasah is essentially the madrasah's manager in this context. The head of a madrasah is required to possess a number of managerial abilities and skills as a manager in the education sector.

As a manager, the head of a madrasah has a significant role to play in improving the quality of education provided by the madrasah. He or she must also consider a significant role that not only influences but also encourages subordinates to use their managerial and technical skills to complete daily tasks. As a result, managers are expected to have a long-term vision and a strategy for the organization. The head of a madrasah needs the right plan in place to enable all of the madrasah's resources to achieve educational objectives in order for them to carry out their responsibilities as a manager. How the management functions or processes, namely planning, organizing, leadership, controlling, and controlling, are implemented is closely related to the managerial skills of the principal, who are adept at coordinating, mobilizing, and harmonizing all existing resources.

According to Handyaningrat (1998), a manager must possess the following three skills: technical skills (technical skills) are the skills of using methods, processes, procedures, and techniques to carry out work in this case, especially in the field of education. Conceptual skills are the ability to know the overall policy of the organization. Human skills are the ability to communicate and build coordination within groups or with other groups.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Technical skills are everything related to the job, including knowledge, abilities, and skills. (2004) Jawwad Or on the other hand the abilities expected to make a particular showing. "Technical skill is the ability to use the knowledge, methods, techniques, and equipment needed to carry out certain tasks obtained from experience, education, and training," Paul asserts. 1997, Hersey) A manager with technical skills needs to be proficient in language and administrative skills (the capacity to direct the administration department). And faculty mastery in work that is a specialty (Winardi, 2015), naturally, the head of the madrasah as faculty manager works in education.

Leading managers need to master most of the technical skills. because education officers, particularly teachers, are directly interacting with front-line managers. The supervisors and front-line managers who are tasked with directing and supervising the teachers' work (Pidarta, 2007). The principal chief in an instructive organization is, obviously, the top of the madrasa. In this context, technical ability refers to the capacity to carry out one's work in accordance with a predetermined strategy. This stage implies that the

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head of the madrasah develops operational procedures for educational establishments, provides examples of how to work, inspires, and collaborates with various educational components at all times. Professionalism and seriousness are required to implement good literacy. As a controlling manager, the principal of the madrasa must be able to perform management supervisory tasks, which entail supervising in the areas of skill development, administrative and institutional competence, and teaching supervision, which entails supervising and controlling the abilities and tasks of students. As a result, the madrasah's head must be competent and skilled in his interactions with his staff.

On the basis of the preceding explanation, it is possible to emphasize that the principal possesses the following technical skills: Leading expertise in curriculum use, classroom management, supervision, quality improvement, and administration, infrastructure, and finance. The Head's skills include special expertise and knowledge in a particular facility-related activity, namely how to use tools and methods to carry out activities.

Quality of Education

The Concept of Quality Education

Quality is an organized interaction to further develop the subsequent item. Management quality means more than average at an affordable cost (Jerome). "State, level or degree (intelligence, intelligence, etc.)," according to the extensive Indonesian dictionary (Alwi Hasan and others, 2005). Nasution cites Carvin as saying that quality is "a dynamic condition related to the results obtained, human or labor, processes and tasks, and the environment that meets or exceeds the expectations of its customers or consumers." "Quality is in accordance with the implied or standardized (conformance to requirement), namely in accordance with the quality standards that have been determined, both input, process, and output," according to Crosby. In this instance, there are two perspectives on the definition of quality: normative and descriptive. In the normative sense, criteria (inner and outer factors) are used to determine quality. The quality of education is a product of education, namely reaping those who are educated according to ideal standards, based on intrinsic criteria. An instrument for educating a skilled workforce is extrinsic criteria for the quality of education. From an unmistakable perspective, quality is resolved in light of an assertion. for instance, the outcomes of assessments of learning achievement.

The ability of madrasahs to operate in a structured and effective manner toward the madrasah-related components in order to produce added value to these components in accordance with applicable norms and standards is what defines quality education. One interpretation of some of the aforementioned definitions is that a quality education is one that is capable of producing graduates with the ability and competence in their fields, based on personal and social competences. Madrasahs need to be able to carry out management that is based on improving the quality of education at these madrasahs in order to improve the quality of education.

The two definitions of quality that are used in the context of education are: the quality of the learning process and the learning outcomes." Teaching materials (cognitive, affective, or psychomotor), learning

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methodologies that vary depending on the ability of teachers, appropriate learning media, and learning resources are all components of quality in the context of the educational process.

Strategies in Improving the Quality of Education

According to Soetopo (2005), educational outcomes are considered high-quality products if they meet one or more of the following criteria: a) Students demonstrate a high level of mastery of learning tasks in accordance with educational goals, including sports scores; b) Educational outcomes are in accordance with needs; c) Educational outcomes are appropriate and relevant to environmental demands. particularly the universe of work. The following elements must be taken into consideration in order to raise the standard of education provided by madrasas: strong and positive leadership in the madrasah, high expectations, challenges to students' thinking, progress monitoring, student responsibility and involvement in the madrasah, prizes and incentives, and people's involvement in the madrasah furthermore, predictable preparation and approach.

It is necessary to apply the following supporting criteria in order for educational institutions to have advantages and be accepted by users of education services: Application of Educational Management Professionalism, the Education Sector's Implementation of Integrated Quality Management, the Enforcement of Education's Legality, and the Improvement of Educational Accreditation Institutions' Performance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study employs a qualitative methodology (Sugiyono, 2007; Aslan, 2019). Because the research is conducted in natural settings and the data and analysis are more qualitative, qualitative methods are frequently referred to as naturalistic research methods. In order to demonstrate the roundness of the case life cycle and the overall interaction of the factors in the cases studied, the researcher intends to employ a qualitative methodology in which cases are given greater attention and greater detail. This kind of case study research is used by researchers with the goal of providing a comprehensive description of the Managerial Madrasah Principals' role in enhancing education quality and furthering their scientific understanding of the Managerial Madrasah.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Central's Specialized Abilities in Working on the Nature of Schooling

Specialized abilities with an end goal to work on the nature of madrasah training can be brought out through a few capacities or abilities, to be specific: a) effectively managing the class, such as through the use of a boarding school or an integrated education system between Hadisiyah and Salafiyah; b) Creating an integrated madrasah curriculum, which is a system that combines the formal education curriculum as defined by the Ministry of National Education or the Ministry of Religion, the curriculum of an Islamic boarding school, and the curriculum of Arabic and English language training institutions; c) Continuously

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improving the quality of education, specifically by evaluating programs that have been implemented within a predetermined time frame. As a result of this evaluation, any areas in need of improvement will be addressed; d) In an effort to improve the quality of learning, regularly supervise teachers in particular; e) Supervise madrasah financial management as well as facility and infrastructure administration. It should be understood that a top educational institution manager should have mastered technical skills. This is due to the fact that managers of educational establishments interact directly with education officers, particularly teachers. A supervisor, the education manager—in this case, the madrasah principal—is responsible for directing and supervising the teachers so that they can teach as effectively as possible. In addition, it is the responsibility of the madrasah principal to cultivate, develop, enhance, and expand existing resources in order to raise the standard of education provided by schools. The principal must be technically capable of putting programs into action in the field within the context of coaching. The principal will have difficulty providing maximum direction if they lack technical skills.

Technical skills, such as mastering knowledge of methods, processes, procedures, and techniques to carry out special activities and being able to utilize and empower the facilities and equipment that are available, are necessary for the principal to effectively perform his role as a manager. Needed to help these particular activities.

The madrasah principal's responsibilities can be broken down into two categories:

a) Tasks in administration; also,

b) obligations in the field of oversight. In the administrative sphere, the madrasah principal's responsibilities fall into two categories: issues pertaining to the technical administration and development of education and teaching, such as program improvement and teaching education activities, in order to create a better teaching and learning environment, and management pertaining to teaching management, staffing, students, buildings and courtyards, finance, and management of school and community relations.

As a result, madrasah principals require technical expertise in order to effectively supervise their staff. The head of the madrasah must master the technical implementation of education in his institution because he is fully responsible for the advancement or decline of education there. For the nature of instruction to be accomplished, madrasahs need to make customary framework enhancements. Because the management, personnel, planning, new admissions, and teaching systems all serve as the foundation for quality improvement steps, The quality of the final product improves with improved implementation of the system. In contrast, a poor system will also lead to poor quality.

CONCLUSION

The following are the findings of the research on the skills of the head of madrasah in improving the quality of education at MAN Insan Cendekia Sambas West Kalimantan, based on data exposure, research findings, and discussion:

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The Head of MAN Insan Cendekia Sambas West Kalimantan has the following technical skills for raising the standard of education: a) The capacity to effectively manage classes in both the boarding school system and the Salafiyah-Hadisiyah integrated education system; b) The capacity to develop madrasah curricula using a system that combines the Islamic boarding school curriculum and language training institution curriculum (Arabic and English) with the formal education curriculum as defined by the Ministry of National Education or the Ministry of Religion; c) The capacity to continuously raise educational quality within a predetermined time frame through planned evaluations; d) The capacity to oversee teachers in an effort to enhance learning quality; e) The capacity to oversee madrasah financial management as well as facility and infrastructure administration.

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